

Tactical Green Marketing Orientation: A Tool for Achieving Environmental Performance of SMEs in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

SMEs have long been recognized as notable engines that contribute to the growth and development of the economy. The lack of awareness, limited government incentives, and low environmental literacy are challenges facing the environmental performance of the SMEs. Tactical green marketing orientation represents a flexible strategy as an option to the SMEs in their intent to reduce their adverse impact on the natural environment, however how and when to venture along with the greener production remain a far greater challenge. This study seeks to evaluate the relationship between tactical green marketing orientation and environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state. The study adopted an explanatory research design targeting employees of manufacturing SMEs operators in Oyo state while sample sizes of 384 were determined using Taro Yamane's formula. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed with regression analytical technique to test hypotheses. The findings indicated that green product has a significant and positive effect on environmental performance ($t= 15.180$, $P\text{-value} = 0.000$); and green promotion has a significant and positive effect on environmental performance ($t=14.480$, $P\text{-value} = 0.000$). Furthermore, tactical green marketing orientation has positive and statistically significant effect on environmental performance ($t= 5.286$, $P\text{-value} = 0.00$; $t= 4.929$, $P\text{-value} = 0.00$). It is therefore recommended that SMEs should continue to develop product packages that are re-usable, recyclable and biodegradable to stay competitive in the business environment; and to engage in activities that aid reduction in carbon emission which enhances their environmental value.

Keywords: Environmental performance, Green marketing, Green promotion Small and medium-sized enterprises, Tactical green marketing,

Introduction

Small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) are significant drivers of global economic growth. SMEs account for around 90% of firms in both developed and developing nations, as measured by generating employment, taxes, and influence on GDP. Globally, SMEs are progressively turning green owing to legal demands, consumer preferences, competitive benefits, and poor perceived value from environmentally concerned customers. In Africa, SMEs contribute significantly to economic growth of the continent. The presence of SMEs in every sector of the economy, contributes to the environmental degradation of the continent due to limited sustainable practices (Adebayo et al., 2021). In South Africa, Kenya, and Ghana, some of the SMEs have gradually embraced sustainable practices as a result of increasing eco-consciousness and international trade pressures (Muposhi et al., 2022). In Nigeria, the continent's largest economy, SMEs exist in practically every industry and play a significant role in the country's progress. Notable evidence includes diversifying and growing the industrial base, using local resources and labour, boosting government revenue, producing wealth, lowering poverty, and minimising rural-to-urban migration, among other things. SMEs in Nigeria are the engines of economic development, and they serve as the backbone of Nigerian economy (Obi, 2015). Nigeria is faced with severe environmental challenges, including pollution and waste mismanagement, exacerbated by industrial and SME activities (Ekwueme et al., 2023). While few Nigerian SMEs engage in basic green practices, systematic tactical green marketing orientation (TGMO) adoption remains rare among many of them due to limited government incentives, poor infrastructure, and low environmental literacy (Ogbonna, et al., 2022). However, rising global sustainability trends and local environmental advocacy are pushing SMEs toward greener marketing strategies (Akinade et al., 2021). Few SMEs in today's Nigeria have adopted the "green" idea, which is evident in how they conduct businesses, how they protect the environment, and how they want their clients to see them in terms of their commitment to the environment (Daniel, 2019).

From the public point of view, environmental performance is how well an organization minimizes its negative ecological impact while promoting sustainability through its operations, products, and marketing strategies. In green marketing, environmental performance is measured by the extent to which a firm adopts eco-friendly practices in product design, distribution, and promotion. Similarly, designing of products for durability, repairability, and recyclability is a form of waste reduction, and a performance of environmental responsibility. Composting organic waste and using recycled materials in production can lower environmental impact, which is the benefit from adopting the 3Rs (reduce, reuse, recycle) in minimizing landfill waste (Ghisellini et al., 2016). A small furniture firm using reclaimed wood to minimize deforestation is actively and consciously protecting the environment. A textile business using waterless dyeing techniques to conserve water

is practically reducing pollution of the environment (Bocken et al., 2016; & UNEP, 2000). TGMO allows strategic integration of environmentally friendly practices in product design, distribution, and promotion to enhance environmental performance (Leonidou et al., 2013). TGMO provides flexibility to SMEs wanting to conserve or improve the natural environment by saving energy or decreasing pollutants. Research has shown that barely 5% of Nigerians engage in green purchasing behavior, despite the fact that the country is very attentive to environmental issues and green marketing. The study noted that the Nigerian society also faces issues like a lack of understanding of green products, a lack of environmental consciousness, insufficient government regulation, rising pricing for green products, and mistrust of so-called green products (Oseremen, 2019). The topic of whether a tactical green marketing strategy can boost product sales with minimal harm to the environment is still open for investigation.

Statement of the Problem

The year 2000s saw the rise of tactical GMO, with SMEs leveraging short-term green initiatives for environmental performance (Leonidou et al., 2013b). Ideally, green product practices ensure that products that emanate from SMEs are processed and designed to have minimal impact on the environment as well as targeted consumers, by utilizing sustainable materials that make the products recyclable, reusable, biodegradable, conserving resources and allowing for energy renewal (Dangelico & Vocalelli, 2017; Ottman, 2017; Leonidou et al., 2013b; Leonidou et al., 2015; Jahroh et al., 2022). Similarly, green promotion practices are noticed with SMEs treating their product information with clarity, stating the benefits, safety features, and engaging in active digital promotion and campaign to meet the yearnings of eco-friendly consumers, who are more likely to support brands that demonstrate environmental responsibility. The reality of ground however reveals that the implementation of green product and green promotion as components of TGMO by SMEs hardly conform to environmental sustainability. A few studies have examined the relationship between tactical green marketing orientation and environmental performance of SMEs (Mohsen & Hossein, 2018; Papadas et al., 2017; Khan et al., 2023; Choudhury et al., 2019). Other studies indicate that SMEs with strong TGMO achieve better environmental performance by reducing waste, lowering carbon footprints, and enhancing resource efficiency (Chen & Chang, 2013). They all revealed that TGMO has positive and significant effect on purchase behavior and environmental performance of firms. Furthermore, extant studies on influence of TGMO on environmental performance of SMEs have not been adequately researched in Nigeria's business environment. Hence, this study is conducted to investigate the relationship between tactical green marketing orientation and environmental performance of SMEs in Oyo state, Nigeria. The study's objectives are to: (i) assess the effects of green product on the environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state; (ii) examine the effects of green promotion on the environmental

performance of selected; (iii) investigate the effects of tactical green marketing orientation and environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state.

The following hypotheses were formulated in a null form and tested:

- (i) **H₀₁**: Green product does not affect environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state;
- (ii) **H₀₂**: Green promotion does not enhance environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state; and
- (iii) **H₀₃**: Tactical green marketing orientation does not affect environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state.

Literature Review

Environmental Performance

With the necessity for sustainable human growth, promoting environmental preservation has taken on new dimension. Deterioration of the environment, pressure from international organisations, government initiatives, the campaign to go green, and the influence of public media have all contributed to the environmental dilemma becoming a global one. This has broadened the development of green marketing, which represents an expansive market for environmentally and socially conscious goods and services. Environmental factors must be taken into account in all facets of marketing, including new product creation and communications (Jacob, 2001). Some firms continue to function in the traditional way, manufacturing goods for customers depending on their whims and preferences. Some people neglect to acknowledge that client awareness has moved to the forefront of the market nowadays. Instead of just purchasing anything on the market, customers increasingly favor products that are ecologically favorable to them (Ebhote & Oseghale, 2019). A proper evaluation of environmental performance comprises pollutants minimization, quality enhancement, recycle efficiency, various stakeholders' perception, reducing waste, consumption of resources, as well as cost-saving. Managers have critical role in attaining environmental performance goals by way of recruiting, educating, evaluating, and rewarding environmentally conscientious employees (Renwick ET AL, 2019). The concern that a corporation has for environmental problems that arise is also influenced by factors like the firm's size, the size of its board of directors, profitability, leverage, public ownership, multinational ownership, or corporate profile (Mahrani & Soewarno, 2018; Aliyu, 2019). Environmental protection-related corporate innovativeness offers the business an edge over its rivals (Agustia et al., 2019). And by communicating the outcome of firm's environmental performance, such organisation is position to win public's trust (Ramadhan et al., 2019).

Environmental Values

Environmental values refer to the conviction that firms have for extending beyond the conventional economic bounds of the enterprise and tying to ecological values (Thelken & De Jong, 2020). As they are linked to business goals, values are significant indicators of a SME operator's or potential entrepreneur's attitude, thinking, and behavior toward sustainable business (Nuringsih & Puspitowati, 2017). In order to find better ways to decrease waste or deal with issues brought on by natural resource scarcities, SME operators also need to be pushed to seek sustainable companies. This value is often reflected in the willingness to invest in practices and technologies that minimize environmental impacts. The importance of environmental value has surged due to increased awareness of environmental issues such as climate change, resource depletion, and biodiversity loss. Environmental value influences consumer behavior, leading to increased demand for sustainable products and services. Studies have shown that consumers are willing to pay a premium for products that are perceived as environmental friendly, as this reflects their commitment to sustainability (Nielsen, 2015). Environmental value fosters strong relationships with stakeholders, including employees, investors, communities, and governments.

Customer Satisfaction

It is widely believed that satisfied customers are more likely to remain loyal, contribute positively to word-of-mouth marketing, and increase profitability for businesses. Customer satisfaction is the perception of customer towards the value received from a product or service compared to their expectations (Kotler et al, 2018). This plays a crucial role in customers' retention or recall, loyalty, recommendation, repetition and advocacy for the product, which are essential for long-term business success. A study revealed that 66% of global consumers have risen to 73% especially among Millennials who are willing to pay more for sustainable goods (Nielsen, 2015). This indicates a strong consumer demand for products that are environmentally friendly and for companies that prioritize sustainability. This trend is not just about altruism; many consumers believe that sustainable products are of higher quality and safer to use. Therefore, companies that meet these expectations are likely to see an increase in customer satisfaction. When implemented correctly, green promotion can enhance brand loyalty and customer satisfaction. A study found that consumers, who perceive a brand as environmentally responsible, are more likely to feel a stronger emotional connection to that brand (Hartmann & Ibáñez, 2007; Ayedogbon, & Oyedokun, 2023). This emotional connection can translate into higher levels of customer satisfaction and loyalty. Conventionally, customer satisfaction metrics, such as: Customer Satisfaction Score (CSAT) and Net Promoter Score (NPS); have been used to assess how sustainability efforts are perceived by customers. However, it is also important to measure the emotional connection that

customers feel with a brand, as this can be a significant driver of satisfaction. Surveys and customer feedback are valuable tools for gauging customer perceptions of a company's sustainability efforts. As environmental concerns continue to grow, sustainability is likely to become an even more important factor in customer satisfaction. Companies who fail to prioritize sustainability may find themselves at a competitive disadvantage, as consumers increasingly choose brands that align with their values. Consumers are increasingly demanding that companies provide detailed information about their environmental impact and the steps they are taking to reduce it (Nguyen et al., 2020). Companies that are transparent about their sustainability efforts and are willing to be held accountable for their actions are likely to see higher levels of customer satisfaction.

Green Marketing

Environmental conservation is the major concern of green marketing. Many environmental challenges have arisen as a result of modern marketing. The economic downturn worldwide, post-Brexit issues, as well as transformations in the panorama of social responsibility in business are putting pressure on management to include sustainability measures into the firm's marketing strategy. The result is green marketing (GM), a novel marketing concept, regarded as one of the biggest innovations in contemporary marketing (Gurau & Ranchhod, 2005). GM has been around since the mid-1960s. Ever since then, varying phrases (environmental, ecological, sustainable marketing) and descriptions employed in the field have led to misconceptions of GM, affiliating it phenomenally with different product attributes such as reusable, refillable, efficient engines, less contaminating, as well as recyclable. Green marketing is defined as marketing actions conducted by businesses with the goal of increasing a product's positive effect or decreasing its adverse effect on the environment (Jain & Kaur, 2004; Oyedokun, G.E., & Garba, 2022). GM focuses on creating goods that meet the demands of customers while being environmentally beneficial. GM has grown over the last 60 years, according to an examination of its growth. There is no question that GM is still growing, and there is a chance that GMO (green marketing orientation) may soon extend beyond the limitations of the sustainable stage.

GMO is an organisational culture that incorporates green ethical standards into the company's plan of action and overall operations. The GMO stands for "the extent in which an organisation gets involved with tactical, strategic, and administrative operations and procedures with a goal of developing, teaming up, and delivering goods and services with less adverse environmental impact (Papadas et al., 2017)." The dimension of GMO construct is conceptualized in this study as a collection of aspects, including: internal green marketing orientation, tactical green marketing orientation and strategic green marketing orientation. Strategic green marketing orientation (SGMO) is a term that refers to long-term, top management initiatives and practices that are

particularly centered on organizational environmental strategy, proactive environmental strategies, as well as external environmental stakeholders. Tactical green marketing orientation (TGMO) entails quick changes, that create a greener version of the conventional marketing mix. The component encompasses measures to enhance environmental sustainability in supply chain, modify pricing procedures for green products, product-related decisions to lessen the ecological footprint, and advertising techniques that lessen the adverse ecological effects of the firm's marketing communication and communicate products' environmental (Chen, 2001). These strategies provide flexibility to businesses looking to conserve energy and reduce pollution in order to safeguard and benefit the environment (Zhu & Sarkis, 2004). Internal green marketing orientation (IGMO) establishes a more pervasive corporate green culture, entailing the cross-pollination of environmental principles within the firm (Papadas et al., 2017). However, the focus of this study is on tactical green marketing orientation which is further discussed.

Green Product

Product is the most crucial component when a firm implements green marketing plan. Product is the core of the mix. The terms "green product," "ecological product," and "environmentally friendly product" are used interchangeably (Shalash, 2022; Sajeewanie et al., 2019). However, these phrases also contain the definition that "green products" refer to goods with little to no negative environmental effect. A "green product" is one that is created to meet a valid human need and poses no risk to the environment or human health (Shalash, 2022). The development of a "green product" entails giving the product an ecological dimension through the use of recyclable packaging, biodegradable and toxic-free materials (Leonidou et al., 2015). Green products must not only be valuable based on firm's perspective only, but also in the eyes of consumers. Through marketing communications, any discrepancy between the attributes of green products as they are perceived and as they are actually, must be closed (Dangelico & Vocalelli, 2017). The positions of the scholars on green products could be summarized as referring to any good or service that is being sold to meet the need or desire of the consumers with lower negative environmental effect.

Green Promotion

Green promotion involves strategies for how a company interacts with customers regarding its promises, actions, and performance in terms of environmental protection. Customers are informed that the items are ecologically friendly and sustainable, which encourages them to buy (Ariffin et al., 2016). It takes many different forms, including personal selling, emails, advertisements, and media campaigns, all of which are intended to put the firm and its products in a green light. Personal selling may be quite successful, but the sales team must be well-versed on the advantages

of the product in order to communicate them to clients. Green advertising has become increasingly popular as a result of businesses' increased demands to tell customers who care about the environment with their goods and services (Masocha, 2021). It transmits messages that reflect the demands and expectations of the environmentally conscious interested party in terms of ecology, environmental sustainability, or eco-friendliness (Masocha, 2021). Green promotions might consist of a company that sponsored the world cup rally and ran a campaign "environmental car of the year" to let people know that they did not have to buy new cars because they can use their old vehicles and still be environmental with the new era of renewable fuels (Lucia & Ibokette, 2020). A study stresses the significance of eco-branding, some firms' logos and brand names show their commitment to environmental protection. Green promotion is important for consumer education for environmental sustainability; therefore, information about green products should be concise and straightforward, and marketers of green products should be strategic in how they market their products in a more attractive manner (Baker, 2012). However, it is easier to do this in traditional marketing than green marketing, because when using terms like "biodegradable," "recyclable," and "environmentally friendly" in promoting goods, the marketing promoters might be having difficulty communicating an understandable meaning (Hoque et al., 2018). Therefore, instead of green product and service having an identifiable meaning, there are several brands that savour them to provide confusion and loss of understanding with its complexity (Hasan & Ali, 2015). It also frustrates the marketer to use the word at all, because green concepts are difficult to identify and measure, it makes it almost impossible for companies to market their green products. So, instead of allocating more resources towards green product, some just cease doing so (Hoque et al., 2018).

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

The Small and Medium Business Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) reported 84 percent in 2013 via the Nigerian Bureau of Statistics. It divides SMEs into four categories: large, micro, small and medium business. SMEs have between 5 and 250 employees. SMEs are critical to the growth of any economy due to their enormous potential for creating jobs, advancing technology domestically, broadening the country's production, nurturing home-grown innovators as well as harmonizing large-scale businesses. Nigeria has sadly failed immensely in the SMEs sub-sector, which limits the ability of SMEs to contribute to the economic development in the sector (Oyedokun, Olatayo, & Adeyemo, 2023). There are several challenges confronting the SMEs, including a hostile business climate, inadequate finance, inadequate managerial skills and restricted technological access comparable to that of the developed countries. If SMEs employ 50 percent of the population, then people who buy items are likely to be from the working class. While larger businesses, often international companies; have already been building the capabilities needed to accomplish environmental sustainability; SMEs, in their opinion, obviously lacks the

technical proficiency or knowledge to counteract green obstacles, and their outlook on the future of technology was somewhat restricted (Amegbe et al., 2017; **Oyedokun, Olakunle, & Adeyemi, 2024**). There is still a gap between environmental understanding, the goals of SMEs, and the total purchasing behavior of the customer. A study concurred that investigating variables that impact their green purchasing behavior is crucial in understanding their green purchasing behavior and making them the embassies in pushing others to consume green products (Wahid et al., 2011).

Stakeholder Theory

The advent of the stakeholder approach to strategy is R. Edward Freeman's book where he formalized the concept Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach (Freeman, 1984). The conventional perspective of the company holds that its shareholders are its owners, and it has a responsibility to give them first priority and must take just four parties' demands into consideration: investors, employees, both customers and providers. Stakeholder theory, however, believes there are more parties that fit this process, for example, the public, government organizations, political groups, communities, labour organizations and even rival businesses. Freeman argues that businesses should consider the needs of all parties affected by their operations, rather than focusing solely on maximizing shareholder profits. The theory challenges the traditional shareholder-centric view, by arguing that businesses have obligations to a new range of actors; employees, customers, suppliers, the community and the natural environment (Freeman, 1984; Friedman, 1970). A stakeholder, in Freeman's view, is a person or group that has the potential to influence or be influenced by business goals (Freeman, 2008). Companies must fulfill stakeholder expectations, one of which is connected to environmental performance, because stakeholders have the power to govern and influence how the firm uses its resources (Sarkis et al., 2011). Scholars and practitioners at the time joined in expanding and supporting Stakeholder Theory. They argued that firms perform better when they address stakeholder interests. Despite the widespread acceptance of the Stakeholder Theory, the theory did attract criticism from few scholars. A study argued that a firm's sole responsibility is to increase shareholder wealth, and stakeholder considerations dilute managerial focus (Friedman, 1970). The fundamental tenet of the stakeholder theory is that stakeholders are vital to a firm's success because they affect a firm's long-term strategic priorities (Andersen, 2008; Aarseth et al., 2011). Stakeholder Theory is particularly relevant to SMEs adopting green products for improved environmental performance for many reasons. Investors and financial institutions sometime favour green businesses, providing loans and incentives for SMEs (Eccles et al., 2014). Disregard to environmental stakeholders can lead to reputational damage, legal penalties, and lost opportunities (Clarkson, 1995). The theory's emphasis on ethical and inclusive business practices makes it indispensable and relevant to this study as well as in the context of environmental sustainability.

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) is a psychological theory which explains and predicts human behaviour and is grounded in cognitive mental processes. TPB is a conceptual extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), which continues to improve "A model of Predicting and Changing Behaviour," developed by Icek Ajzen (1985, 1991) to include behaviours that are not fully under volitional control (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975; Ajzen, 1985). TPB describes that human behaviour is influenced by three key determinants: attitudes, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control, which combine to influence their intentions to behave and their actions (actual behaviour) (Ajzen, 1985; Ajzen, 1991). Attitude toward the behaviour (ATT) refers to an individual's positive or negative evaluation to performing a behaviour. Subjective Norm (SN), on the other hand, refers to the pressure perceived from one's important group (family, peers and society), to undertake or not undertake the behaviour. Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) is how easy or difficult an individual exhibits the behaviour, as a result of past experiences and expected obstacles. The three stated determinants (ATT, SN, and PBC) serve as input that will shape the output - behavioural intentions and subsequent action of an individual. The theory has consistently been applied in marketing to understand consumer purchase intentions (Paul et al., 2016). Despite the widespread adoption of the theory, TPB had faced several criticisms from different quarters. A study criticized the theory for its overemphasis on rational decision-making. Critics argue that emotions and unconscious biases are under-represented (Sniehotta et al., 2014). The Theory of Planned Behaviour is pertinent to green promotion (eco-friendly marketing) which aim is to influence consumer behaviour towards sustainable choices. If individual consumers believe they can access sustainable products easily enough and afford it, they are more likely to purchase it (Yadav & Pathak, 2016). The TPB is considered a robust model for understanding behavioural intentions, particularly in green marketing. Its structured approach helps SMEs design effective eco-friendly promotions that enhance customer satisfaction by aligning with consumer attitudes, social norms, and perceived control.

Research Methods

An explanatory research design was chosen to gather information in order to evaluate the causal relationships between the variables that were observed. The population of the study is 9,340 consisting of middle and operational level personnel of the manufacturing SMEs operators in Oyo state. There are thirty three local government areas (LGA) in Oyo state, each local government area is zoned into five areas namely: Ibadan (11 LGA and 157,514 registered MSME), Oke-ogun (10 LGA and 75,854 registered MSME), Ogbomoso (5 LGA and 125,862 registered MSME), Oyo (4 LGA and 110,316 registered MSME) and Ibarapa (3 LGA and 68,175 registered MSME) making a total MSME of 537,721 (THISDAY Newspaper, 2023; SMEDAN, 2023). The study

focuses on SMEs - (Small and Medium Enterprises) with minimum employees' requirement in place and some levels of tactical operations in Oyo state. The nano and micro enterprises are outside of the scope of this study because they do not major as manufacturing operators.

The study population is derived from the selected SMEs in the three local government areas in Ibadan (Zone), Oyo state, as shown in Table 3.1 below. Oluyole has 3,024, Ibadan North east has 3,481, and Ibadan South East has 2,835, making a total of (9,340). The rationale for the choice of these LGA is because they are hubs for top multi-national, regional and local firms who engage in the production of goods, and whose operations have interface with their surrounding environment.

To be included in the sample study, the researcher ensures that the manufacturing SMEs investigated have tactical green marketing practices in place so as to furnish the study with appropriate data. Having determined the population size, the sample size was obtained using Taro-Yamane's formula (Taro, 1967). As a result, 384 is the sample size, and it accurately represents the research population. This suggests that the respondents will receive 384 copies of the questionnaire. However, the study used the Bowley (1996) proportional allocation formula to calculate the percentage of the questionnaire that should be given to participants in each of the selected LGAs where the enterprises are situated (Kalapapa, 2020; Fakidouma & Ndubuisi-Okolo, 2023). Questionnaire allocation to Oluyole is 124, Ibadan North east is 143, and Ibadan South East is 117. For the selection of participants in Oluyole, Ibadan North East, and Ibadan South East local government areas, a purposive sampling technique is used. This ensures that only employees of manufacturing SMEs operators who belong to the target population are enrolled in the sample study. The use of primary data was justified by the nature of the investigation. The questionnaire was segmented into three sections, namely: section A, B, and C. Section A addresses respondents' profiles such as: gender, age, qualification, years of operation, and legal status; Section B addresses questions associated with the green product (five questions) as adapted (Davari & Strutton, 2014; Papadas et al., 2017; Eneizan et al., 2019); and green promotion (five questions) as adapted (Hardeep et al., 2014; Roy & Vezina, 2001). Section C contains questions to measure the environmental performance of SMEs being investigated – environmental value (five questions) and customer satisfaction (five questions). Questions in section C were adequately thought of and developed by the researcher as adopted (Singh et al., 2019; Amegbe et al., 2017; Gikonyo et al., 2022; Rutere, 2020; Harini et al., 2020; Grigaliunait & Pileliene, 2016; Yadav et al., 2016). The questions in section B and C were structured based on a five-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). This agrees with the suggestion of Hewitt-Dundas (2004), there is a possibility that using the Likert Scale in the questionnaire technique will be advantageous since it can influence different attitude levels.

Validity and Reliability

Both content and face validity were employed in validating the research tool. A pilot study involving middle and operational level employees of manufacturing SMEs was conducted using 10% of the sample size. The Cronbach's alpha test, which has a range of 0 to 1, was used to evaluate the validity and reliability of the research tool. The reliability coefficient of each variable in research questions was obtained as follow:

Cronbach's Alpha Test for Reliability

S/N	Variables	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Green Product	5	0.900
2	Green Promotion	5	0.909
3	Environmental Value	5	0.788
4	Customer Satisfaction	5	0.747

Source: Computed by the Researcher (2025)

Data Analysis Method

The study adopted a quantitative data analysis method, done with the aid of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) Software Version 26.0. The analysis involves descriptive and inferential statistical tool: Descriptive statistical tools employed include the frequency distribution percentages, means, and standard deviation to analyse responses in the questionnaire. Inferential statistical tool deployed in the study is regression analytical technique; to test the four hypotheses proposed. Three hundred and eighty-four (384) questionnaires were distributed; three hundred and fifty-seven (357) questionnaires were returned, yielding a response rate of 92.9%.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Green product does not affect environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.627 ^a	0.394	0.392	0.20443

a. Predictors: (Constant), Green Product

Source: Researcher's Field Result (2025)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.630	1	9.630	230.422	0.000 ^b
	Residual	14.837	355	0.042		
	Total	24.467	356			

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Green Product

Source: Researcher's Field Result (2025)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.465	0.066		37.177	0.000
	Green Product	0.305	0.020	0.627	15.180	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Performance

Source: Researcher's Field Result (2025)

The table above shows the variables included in the model that contributed to the prediction of the dependent variable. The coefficient table indicates the amount of change one could expect in the dependent given a unit change in the value of the variable. In this table, the beta coefficient for green product in the unstandardized coefficient is ($\beta = 0.305$). This means that green product is recognized and pursued by many SMEs. The coefficients show that green product activities among SMEs is strong. The table also explained that green product and environmental performance is ($t = 15.180$, $P\text{-value} = 0.000$); which implies that the variables are below the P -value threshold of 0.05 and above the t -value threshold of 1.96, making the relationship between green product and environmental performance positive and statistically significant. The result showed that an increase in green product would cause an increase in environmental performance by 0.066 standard deviation.

Decision: Based on the above analysis, the result shows that $t\text{-value} = 15.180$ is more than 1.96; and its significant level, $p = 0.00$ is less than 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis, which states that green product does not affect environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state is rejected. Therefore, alternative hypothesis, which states that green product does have a significant effect on environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state is **accepted**.

Hypothesis 2: Green promotion does not enhance environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.609 ^a	0.371	0.370	0.20816

a. Predictors: (Constant), Green Promotion

Source: Researcher's Field Result (2025)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	9.085	1	9.085	209.662	.000 ^b
	Residual	15.382	355	.043		
	Total	24.467	356			

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Green Promotion

Source: Researcher’s Field Result (2025)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	2.000	0.101		19.760	0.000
	Green Promotion	0.399	0.028	0.609	14.480	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Performance

Source: Researcher’s Field Result (2025)

The table above shows the variables included in the model which contributed to the prediction of the dependent variable. The coefficient table indicates the amount of change one could expect in the dependent given a unit change in the value of the variable. In this table, the beta coefficient for green promotion in the unstandardized coefficient is ($\beta= 0.399$). This means that green promotion is recognized and engaged by many SMEs. The coefficients show that green promotion activities among SMEs is strong. The table also explained that green promotion and environmental performance is ($t= 14.480$, $P\text{-value} = 0.000$), which implies that the variables are below the P-value threshold of 0.05 and above the t-value threshold of 1.96, making the relationship between green promotion and environmental performance positive and statistically significant. The result

therefore showed that an increase in green promotion would cause an increase in environmental performance by 0.028 standard deviation.

Decision: Based on the above analysis, the result shows that $t\text{-value} = 14.480$ is more than 1.96; and its significant level, $p = 0.00$ is less than 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis, which states that green promotion does not enhance environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state is rejected. Thus, alternative hypothesis which states that green promotion does have a significant effect on environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state is **accepted**.

Hypothesis 3: Tactical green marketing orientation does not affect environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.705 ^a	0.497	0.493	0.18675

a. Predictors: (Constant), Tactical Green Marketing
Source: Researcher's Field Result (2025)

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.156	3	4.052	116.189	0.000 ^b
	Residual	12.311	353	.035		
	Total	24.467	356			

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Tactical Green Marketing
Source: Researcher's Field Result (2025)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	1.708	0.108		15.749	0.000
	Green Promotion	0.180	0.034	0.275	5.286	0.000
	Green Product	0.135	0.027	0.277	4.929	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Environmental Performance
Source: Researcher’s Field Result (2025)

The table above shows the variables included in the model which contributed to the prediction of the dependent variable. The coefficient table indicates the amount of change one could expect in the dependent given a unit change in the value of the variable. In this table, the beta coefficient for green promotion and green product in the unstandardized coefficient is ($\beta= 0.180$, $\beta= 0.135$) respectively. The table also explained that green promotion and green product has ($t= 5.286$, $P\text{-value} = 0.00$; $t= 4.929$, $P\text{-value} = 0.00$), which implies that the variables are below the P-value threshold of 0.05 and above the t-value threshold of 1.96. Therefore, making the overall relationship between tactical green marketing orientation and environmental performance intention positive and statistically significant. **Decision:** Based on the above analysis, the result shows that t-value is more than 1.96; and its significant level, $p= 0.00$ is less than 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis, which states that tactical green marketing orientation does not affect environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state is rejected. Therefore, alternative hypothesis which states that tactical green marketing orientation does have a significant effect on environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state is **accepted**.

Discussion of Findings

Green product does not affect environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state.

The inferential statistics shows that green product exhibits a positive significant relationship with environmental performance. Thus, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Although, it is important

to note that the relationship between green product and environmental performance is strong ($R^2 = 0.627$). This indicates that the factors that characterize green product are present and strong enough to influence environmental performance. The result from the descriptive analysis shows that SMEs prefer to use product packaging that are re-usable and recyclable. They prefer to use a product label and design that is ecologically friendly; and use a packaging that is biodegradable. Scholars opine that green product can influence environmental performance. They further note that engaging in green product practices is promising (Yu & Ramanathan, 2015). Scholars note that the arrival of innovation especially in products can enhance the firm performance thereby impacting the environmental performance (Ar, 2012).

Green promotion does not enhance environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state. The inferential statistics shows that green promotion exhibits a positive and statistical significant relationship with environmental performance. Thus, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Although, it is important to note that the relationship between green promotion and environmental performance is strong ($R^2 = 0.609$). This indicates that the factors that characterize green promotion are present and strong enough to influence environmental performance. The result from the descriptive analysis shows that there is clarity in environmental information of the product, the products have environmental benefits and features. Scholars opine that green promotion has a positive and significant influence on environmental performance. They further note that green promotion especially green advertising gives incentives to manufacturers to upgrade their strategy to enhance their performance. They further note that small companies cannot easily adopt green strategy due to its increased cost (Wang et al., 2019).

Tactical green marketing orientation does not affect environmental performance of selected SMEs in Oyo state. The inferential statistics shows that tactical green marketing orientation exhibits a positive statistical significant relationship with environmental performance. Thus, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Although, it is important to note that the relationship between tactical green marketing orientation and environmental performance is strong ($R^2 = 0.705$). This indicates that the factors that characterize tactical green marketing orientation are present and strong enough to influence environmental performance. This shows that the combination of green product and green promotion can reinforce and influence environmental performance of SMEs in Oyo state. Scholars opine that tactical green marketing orientation impacts environmental performance. They further explain that the efficiency of a firm in terms of low cost, reduction in environmental pollution, improved awareness tends to affect the

environmental performance of a firm. They further note that tactical green marketing can be a beneficial tool for environmental performance (Choudhury et al., 2019; Khan et al., 2024).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The involvement of green products and promotion aid to minimize environmental footprints and highlights the environmental advantages of tactical green marketing orientation in businesses. The study concludes that tactical green marketing orientation can influence SMEs in Oyo state. The study was able to show that green product has a positive and significant impact on environmental performance of SMEs in Oyo state. The study found that green promotion has a positive and significant impact on environmental performance of SMEs in Oyo state. In addition, the combine effect was analysed and it was found that green promotion contributes more to explaining the impact of tactical green marketing on environmental performance. This showed that SMEs rely on green promotion activities to influence environmental performance. The following recommendations were put forward: (i) SMEs should continue to develop product packages that are re-usable, recyclable and biodegradable to stay competitive in the business environment; and encourage word-of-mouth recommendations by the customers. (ii) SMEs should engage in activities that aids reduction in carbon emission and enhance transport operations. This will improve the coordination of activities with suppliers and customers, thereby enhancing the environmental value. (iii) Managers should strengthen their engagement in green marketing activities as the development of green products, management of transportation, distribution and promotional activities, and creation of reusable and recyclable packaging materials can serve as a means to differentiate their firms from competitors, leading to a performance edge over rivals. The suggestions put forward for future study are: there is need to research other geopolitical zones in South-West Nigeria such as the study focused only on one of the geopolitical zones, which is Oyo state. There is need to engage in mixed methods to strengthen the findings of future research. There is need to increase the sample size in subsequent study to ascertain the level of awareness and rate of adoption of TGMO amongst SMEs. And lastly, there is need to conduct same research amongst SMEs in specific sector especially sectors inimical to environmental well-being.

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